

ON k -PELL-LUCAS NUMBERS CLOSE TO A POWER OF 2

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Abstract

For $k \geq 2$, let $(Q_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ be the k -generalized Pell-Lucas sequence which starts with $0, \dots, 0, 2, 2$ (k terms) and each term afterwards is given by the linear recurrence

$$Q_n^{(k)} = 2Q_{n-1}^{(k)} + Q_{n-2}^{(k)} + \dots + Q_{n-k}^{(k)}, \quad \text{for } n \geq 2.$$

An integer n is said to be close to a positive integer m if n satisfies $|n - m| < \sqrt{m}$. In this paper, we solve the Diophantine inequality $|Q_n^{(k)} - 2^m| < 2^{m/2}$, in positive unknowns k , m , and n .

1. Introduction

Let k, r be integers with $k \geq 2$ and $r \neq 0$. Let the linear recurrence sequence $(G_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ of order k be defined by

$$G_n^{(k)} = rG_{n-1}^{(k)} + G_{n-2}^{(k)} + \dots + G_{n-k}^{(k)},$$

for $n \geq 2$ with the initial conditions

$$G_{-(k-2)}^{(k)} = G_{-(k-3)}^{(k)} = \dots = G_{-1}^{(k)} = 0, \quad G_0^{(k)} = a, \quad \text{and } G_1^{(k)} = b.$$

For $(a, b, r) = (0, 1, 1)$, the sequence $(G_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ is called the k -generalized Fibonacci sequence $(F_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ [8]. For $(a, b, r) = (0, 1, 2)$ and $(a, b, r) = (2, 2, 2)$, the sequence $(G_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ is called the k -generalized Pell sequence $(P_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$ and the k -generalized Pell-Lucas sequence $(Q_n^{(k)})_{n \geq 2-k}$, respectively [14]. The terms of these sequences are called k -generalized Fibonacci numbers, k -generalized Pell numbers, and k -generalized Pell-Lucas numbers, respectively. When $k = 2$, we have the usual Fibonacci, Pell, and Pell-Lucas sequences, $(F_n)_{n \geq 0}$, $(P_n)_{n \geq 0}$, and $(Q_n)_{n \geq 0}$, respectively.

We need the following definition of closeness.

Definition 1. An integer n is said to be *close* to a positive integer m if n satisfies

$$|n - m| < \sqrt{m}.$$

After the introduction of the previous definition by Chern and Cui in 2014 [10], they determined the Fibonacci numbers that are close to a power of 2. Their work was extended by Bravo, Gomez, and Herrera [4], who characterized all terms $F_n^{(k)}$ that are close to a power of 2. In parallel, Aıkel, Irmak, and Szalay [1] studied k -generalized Lucas numbers that are close to powers of 2. More recently, Bachabi and Togbe [2] determined the k -generalized Pell numbers in the same context.

As a continuation of the work done in [2], in this paper we study the k -Pell-Lucas numbers that are close to a power of 2. More precisely, we will prove the following theorem.

Theorem 1. All the solutions $(Q_n^{(k)}, k, n, m)$ of the inequality

$$\left| Q_n^{(k)} - 2^m \right| < 2^{m/2}, \tag{1}$$

in positive integers k, n, m with $k \geq 2$, are given by

$$(2, k, 1, 1), \quad k \geq 2, \quad (6, k, 2, 3), \quad k \geq 2, \quad (16, k, 3, 4), \quad k \geq 3, \\ (34, 2, 4, 5), \quad (260, 3, 6, 8), \quad \text{and} \quad (32774, 4, 11, 15).$$

We deduce the following consequence.

Corollary 1. Let n, m, k be defined as in Theorem 1, the only solutions to the Diophantine equation $Q_n^{(k)} = 2^m$ are

$$Q_1^{(k)} = 2^1 = 2, \quad k \geq 2 \quad \text{and} \quad Q_3^{(k)} = 2^4 = 16, \quad k \geq 3.$$

Note that this theorem gives the solutions to the Diophantine equation

$$Q_n^{(k)} = 2^m + e \quad \text{with} \quad |e| < 2^{m/2}. \tag{2}$$

For the proof of Theorem 1 we use the properties of the k -Pell-Lucas sequence, Baker’s method based on linear forms in logarithms of algebraic numbers, and the Baker-Davenport reduction method [3]. Here, for the reduction method, we will use a modified version of the result due to Bravo, Gómez, and Luca (Lemma 1 of [5]).

2. Preliminary Results

This section is devoted to collecting a few definitions, notations, properties, and results, which will be used in the remainder of this paper.

2.1. Properties of the k -Generalized Pell-Lucas Sequence

The characteristic polynomial of the k -generalized Pell-Lucas sequence is

$$\Phi_k(x) = x^k - 2x^{k-1} - x^{k-2} - \dots - x - 1.$$

The above polynomial is irreducible over $\mathbb{Q}[x]$ and it has one positive real root $\alpha := \alpha(k)$ which is located between $\phi^2(1 - \phi^{-k})$ and ϕ^2 with $\phi = \frac{1+\sqrt{5}}{2}$, and which lies outside the unit circle (see [17]). The other roots are strictly contained in the unit circle. To simplify the notation, we will omit the dependence of α on k whenever no confusion may arise.

The Binet-type formula for $Q_n^{(k)}$, found in [17], is

$$Q_n^{(k)} = \sum_{i=1}^k (2\alpha_i - 2)g_k(\alpha_i)\alpha_i^n = \sum_{i=1}^k \frac{2(\alpha_i - 1)^2}{(k + 1)\alpha_i^2 - 3k\alpha_i + k - 1} \alpha_i^n, \tag{3}$$

where the α_i are the roots of the characteristic polynomial $\Phi_k(x)$ and the function g_k is given by

$$g_k(z) := \frac{z - 1}{(k + 1)z^2 - 3kz + k - 1}, \tag{4}$$

for $k \geq 2$.

Additionally, it was also shown in [17] that the roots located inside the unit circle have a very minimal influence in formula (3), as can be seen by the inequality

$$\left| Q_n^{(k)} - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n \right| < 2, \tag{5}$$

for $n \geq 2 - k$. Furthermore, it was shown by Şiar and Keskin in [17, Lemma 10] that the inequalities

$$\alpha^{n-1} < Q_n^{(k)} < 2\alpha^n \tag{6}$$

hold, for $n \geq 1$ and $k \geq 2$.

Lemma 1 ([6], Lemma 1 and [7], Lemma 2.3). *Let $k \geq 2$ be an integer. Then, we have*

- (a) $0.276 < g_k(\alpha) < 0.5$ and $|g_k(\alpha_i)| < 1$, for $2 \leq i \leq k$.
- (b) $\phi^2(1 - \phi^{-k}) < \alpha < \phi^2$.

Definition 2. Let α be an algebraic number of degree d , let $a > 0$ be the leading coefficient of its minimal polynomial over \mathbb{Z} , and let $\alpha = \alpha^{(1)}, \dots, \alpha^{(d)}$ be its conjugates. The *logarithmic height* of α is defined by

$$h(\alpha) = \frac{1}{d} \left(\log a + \sum_{i=1}^d \log \left(\max\{|\alpha^{(i)}|, 1\} \right) \right).$$

In particular, if $\eta = p/q$ is a rational number with $\gcd(p, q) = 1$ and $q > 0$, then $h(\eta) = \log \max\{|p|, q\}$. For any algebraic numbers α and β , we have the following properties [19, Property 3.3]:

$$\begin{aligned} h(\alpha\beta) &\leq h(\alpha) + h(\beta), \\ h(\alpha \pm \beta) &\leq \log 2 + h(\alpha) + h(\beta). \end{aligned}$$

Moreover, for any integer n ,

$$h(\alpha^n) \leq |n|h(\alpha).$$

With the above notation, Şiar et al. [18] showed that the logarithmic height of $g_k(\alpha)$ satisfies

$$h(g_k(\alpha)) < 5 \log k, \quad \text{for } k \geq 2. \tag{7}$$

Lemma 2. *Let α be the dominant root of the characteristic polynomial $\Phi_k(x)$ and consider the function $g_k(x)$ defined in (4). If $k \geq 50$ and $n > 1$ are integers satisfying $n < \phi^{k/2}$, then the following inequalities hold:*

(i) ([17], Equation 30)

$$|(2\alpha - 2)\alpha^n - 2\phi^{2n+1}| < \frac{4\phi^{2n}}{\phi^{k/2}},$$

(ii) ([17], Lemma 13)

$$|g_k(\alpha) - g_k(\phi^2)| < \frac{4k}{\phi^k}.$$

Lemma 3 ([16], Lemma 2.3). *Let $k \geq 50$ and suppose that $n < \phi^{k/2}$. Then*

$$(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n = \frac{2\phi^{2n+1}}{\phi + 2}(1 + \xi), \quad \text{where } |\xi| < \frac{1.25}{\phi^{k/2}}.$$

2.2. Linear Form in Logarithms

Matveev (Corollary 2.3 of [15]) or (Theorem 9.4 of [9]) proved the following result.

Theorem 2. *Let η_1, \dots, η_s be positive real algebraic numbers in a real algebraic number field \mathbb{K} of degree $d_{\mathbb{K}}$. Let d_1, \dots, d_s be non-zero integers such that*

$$\Gamma := \eta_1^{d_1} \cdots \eta_s^{d_s} - 1 \neq 0.$$

Then

$$-\log |\Gamma| \leq 1.4 \cdot 30^{s+3} \cdot s^{4.5} \cdot d_{\mathbb{K}}^2 (1 + \log d_{\mathbb{K}}) (1 + \log D) \cdot B_1 \cdots B_s,$$

where

$$D \geq \max\{|d_1|, \dots, |d_s|\},$$

and

$$B_j \geq \max\{d_{\mathbb{K}} h(\eta_j), |\log \eta_j|, 0.16\}, \text{ for all } j = 1, \dots, s.$$

2.3. The Reduction Method

Here, we present the following result due to Bravo, Gómez, and Luca (Lemma 1 of [5]), which is a generalization of the results of Baker and Davenport (Lemma of [3]) and Dujella and Pethö (Lemma 5(a) of [11]).

Lemma 4. *Let M be a positive integer, let p/q be a convergent of the continued fraction of an irrational number τ such that $q > 6M$, and let A , B , and μ be real numbers with $A > 0$ and $B > 1$. Further, let $\varepsilon = \|\mu q\| - M \cdot \|\tau q\|$, where $\|\cdot\|$ denotes the distance from the nearest integer. If $\varepsilon > 0$, then there is no solution of the inequality*

$$0 < |m\tau - n + \mu| < AB^{-k},$$

in positive integers m , n , and k with

$$m \leq M \text{ and } k \geq \frac{\log(Aq/\varepsilon)}{\log B}.$$

Note that Lemma 4 cannot be applied for $\mu = 0$ (since then $\varepsilon < 0$). For this case, we use the following technical result from Diophantine approximation, known as Legendre’s criterion. This comes from the theory of continued fractions (see [13], pages 30 and 37).

Lemma 5. *Let τ be an irrational number.*

(i) If x , y are positive integers such that

$$\left| \tau - \frac{y}{x} \right| < \frac{1}{2x^2},$$

then $y/x = p_k/q_k$ is a convergent of τ .

(ii) Let M be a positive real number and $p_0/q_0, p_1/q_1, \dots$ be all the convergents of the continued fraction $[a_0, a_1, a_2, \dots]$ of τ . Let N be the smallest positive integer such that $q_N > M$. Put $a(M) = \max\{a_k : k = 0, 1, \dots, N\}$. Then, the inequality

$$\left| \tau - \frac{y}{x} \right| > \frac{1}{(a(M) + 2)x^2}$$

holds for all pairs (x, y) of integers with $0 < x < M$.

2.4. Other Useful Results

We conclude this section by recalling the following results that we will need.

Lemma 6 (Lemma 2.2 of [20]). *Let $a, x \in \mathbb{R}$. If $0 < a < 1$ and $|x| < a$, then*

$$|\log(1 + x)| < \frac{-\log(1 - a)}{a} \cdot |x|$$

and

$$|x| < \frac{a}{1 - e^{-a}} \cdot |e^x - 1|.$$

Lemma 7 (Lemma 7 of [12]). *If $\ell \geq 1$, $T > (4\ell^2)^\ell$, and $T > x/(\log x)^\ell$, then*

$$x < 2^\ell T (\log T)^\ell.$$

Theorem 3 (Theorem 1 of [4]). *The Diophantine inequality*

$$|F_n^{(k)} - 2^m| < 2^{m/2}$$

has two parametric families of solutions (n, k, m) with $n, k \geq 2$, and $m \geq 0$, namely

1. $(n, k, m) = (t, k, t - 2)$ for $2 \leq t \leq k + 1$, and
2. $(n, k, m) = (k + 2 + t, k, k + t)$ for $0 \leq t \leq \max\{x \in \mathbb{Z} : 2 + x < 2^{1+(k-x/2)}\}$.
3. In addition, we have the sporadic solution $(n, k, m) = (12, 3, 9)$.

Theorem 4 (Theorem 1.1 of [10]). *There are only 8 Fibonacci numbers which are close to a power of 2. Namely, the solutions $(F_n, 2^m)$ of the inequality*

$$|F_n - 2^m| < 2^{m/2}$$

are $(1, 2), (2, 2), (3, 2), (3, 4), (5, 4), (8, 8), (13, 16)$, and $(34, 32)$.

3. Proof of Theorem 1

In this section, we give all details about the proof of our main theorem. We establish some preliminary results.

The following result gives us the bounds of m in terms of n .

Lemma 8. *If (m, n, k) is a solution of Diophantine Inequality (1) with $n \geq 1$, $m \geq 2$, and $n \geq k + 1$, then we have the inequalities*

$$0.69n - 1.69 < m < 1.39n + 3.78.$$

Proof. Combining Inequality (6) with Equation (1), we have

$$2^{m-1} \leq 2^m - 2^{m/2} < Q_n^{(k)} < 2\alpha^n \leq \alpha^{n+2}$$

and

$$\alpha^{n-1} < Q_n^{(k)} < 2^m + 2^{m/2} < 2^{m+1}.$$

Since $2^{m-1} < \alpha^{n+2}$ and $\alpha^{n-1} < 2^{m+1}$, it follows that $(m - 1) \log 2 < (n + 2) \log \alpha$ and $(n - 1) \log \alpha < (m + 1) \log 2$. So, we get

$$(n - 1) \frac{\log \alpha}{\log 2} - 1 < m < (n + 2) \frac{\log \alpha}{\log 2} + 1.$$

Because $\phi^2(1 - \phi^{-2}) < \alpha < \phi^2$, by Lemma 1(b), for $k \geq 2$, we deduce that

$$0.69n - 1.69 < m < 1.39n + 3.78.$$

This finishes the proof of the lemma. □

The following result gives an upper bound of m and n in terms of k .

Lemma 9. *If the integers n , k , and m satisfy Diophantine Equation (2) with $n \geq k + 1$, then we have the following estimates:*

$$n < 1.7 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k \quad \text{and} \quad m < 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k.$$

Proof. Let us express Equation (2) as follows:

$$2^m - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n = Q_n^{(k)} - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n - e.$$

Taking the absolute value of both sides, we obtain

$$|2^m - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n| \leq |Q_n^{(k)} - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n| + |e| < 2 + 2^{m/2}.$$

Dividing through by $(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n$, we get

$$\left| \frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)} \alpha^{-n} 2^m - 1 \right| < \frac{1}{(\alpha - 1)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n} \left(1 + 2^{(m-2)/2} \right).$$

Since the inequalities $0.276 < g_k(\alpha) < 0.5$ hold for $k \geq 2$ (see Lemma 1) and $2^{m-1} < \alpha^{n+2}$, we deduce that

$$\begin{aligned} \left| \frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)} \alpha^{-n} 2^m - 1 \right| &< 5.87 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^n} + \frac{2^{-1/2} (\alpha^{n+2})^{1/2}}{\alpha^n} \right) \\ &< 5.87 \cdot \left(\frac{1}{\alpha^{n/2}} + \frac{2^{-1/2} \cdot \alpha}{\alpha^{n/2}} \right) \\ &< 5.87 \cdot \left(\frac{1 + 2^{-1/2} \cdot \phi^2}{\alpha^{n/2}} \right) \\ &< \frac{16.74}{\alpha^{n/2}}. \end{aligned} \tag{8}$$

Let

$$\Gamma_1 := \frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)} \alpha^{-n} 2^m - 1.$$

Observe that $\Gamma_1 \neq 0$. If $\Gamma_1 = 0$, then $(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n = 2^m$. Using the \mathbb{Q} -automorphisms $\sigma_i : \alpha \mapsto \alpha_i, i \geq 2$, of the Galois extension $\mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ over \mathbb{Q} and Lemma 1, we find that

$$16 \leq 2^m = |g_k(\alpha_i)| |\alpha_i^n| |2\alpha_i - 2| < 4,$$

which is a contradiction. Thus $\Gamma_1 \neq 0$. Now, we can apply Theorem 2 to Γ_1 . Let us consider

$$\eta_1 = \frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)}, \quad \eta_2 = \alpha, \quad \eta_3 = 2, \quad d_1 = 1, \quad d_2 = -n, \quad d_3 = m.$$

The numbers η_1, η_2, η_3 are elements of the number field $\mathbb{K} := \mathbb{Q}(\alpha)$ with $d_{\mathbb{K}} = k$. We have

$$h(\eta_2) = \frac{\log \alpha}{k} < \frac{2 \log \phi}{k} \quad \text{and} \quad h(\eta_3) = \log 2.$$

Moreover, we get

$$\max\{kh(\eta_2), |\log \eta_2|, 0.16\} < 0.97 = A_2,$$

and

$$\max\{kh(\eta_3), |\log \eta_3|, 0.16\} \leq k \log 2 = A_3.$$

Using the properties of the logarithmic height and (7), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} h(\eta_1) &\leq \log 2 + h(\alpha - 1) + h(g_k(\alpha)) \\ &< 2 \log 2 + \frac{\log \alpha}{k} + 5 \log k \\ &< 2 \log 2 + \log \phi + 5 \log k \\ &< 7.8 \log k, \end{aligned}$$

for $k \geq 2$. So, we can take

$$\max\{kh(\eta_1), |\log \eta_1|, 0.16\} < 7.8k \log k = A_1.$$

Finally, from Lemma 8, we can choose $D = 6n > 1.39n + 3.78 \geq \max\{1, m, n\}$, for $n \geq 1$. Thus, Theorem 2 tells us that

$$\log |\Gamma_1| \geq -7.51 \cdot 10^{11} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log k \cdot (1 + \log k)(1 + \log(6n)).$$

By the facts $1 + \log(6n) < 2.3 \log n$ and $1 + \log k < 2.5 \log k$, which hold for $n \geq 9$ and $k \geq 2$, we obtain

$$\log |\Gamma_1| > -4.32 \cdot 10^{12} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k \cdot \log n. \tag{9}$$

Combining Inequalities (8) and (9), we get

$$n < 1.8 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k \cdot \log n.$$

Thus, we obtain

$$\frac{n}{\log n} < 1.8 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k.$$

Applying Lemma 7 with $T = 1.8 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k$, $x = n$, and $\ell = 1$, we have

$$\begin{aligned} n &< 2 \cdot (1.8 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k) \cdot \log(1.8 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k) \\ &< (3.6 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^2 k) \cdot (30.53 + 4 \log k + 2 \log \log k) \\ &< 1.7 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k. \end{aligned} \tag{10}$$

In the above inequalities, we have used the fact that

$$30.53 + 4 \log k + 2 \log(\log k) < 47 \log k$$

holds for $k \geq 2$. Finally, using Inequality (10) and Lemma 8, we obtain

$$m < 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k.$$

This completes the proof of Lemma 9. □

The last preliminary result established is the following lemma.

Lemma 10. *There is no solution for Inequality (1) with $k > 350$ and $n \geq k + 1$.*

Proof. Referring to Lemma 9, we have

$$n < 1.7 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k < \phi^{k/2}, \text{ for } k > 350.$$

Thus, from Lemma 3, Equation (2), and Inequality (5), we have

$$\begin{aligned} \left| 2^m - \frac{2\phi^{2n+1}}{\phi+2} \right| &= \left| \frac{2\phi^{2n+1}}{\phi+2} \xi + Q_n^{(k)} - (2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)\alpha^n - e \right| \\ &< \frac{2.5\phi^{2n+1}}{(\phi+2) \cdot \phi^{k/2}} + 2 + 2^{m/2}. \end{aligned}$$

Multiplying through by $(\phi+2)/2\phi^{2n+1}$, and using the facts that $2 < \phi^2$ and $m < 1.39n + 3.78 < 1.5n$ for $n > 34$ (see Lemma 8), we obtain

$$\begin{aligned} |\Gamma_2| &< \frac{1.25}{\phi^{k/2}} + \frac{\phi+2}{\phi^{2n+1}} + 2^{m/2} \cdot \frac{\phi+2}{2\phi^{2n+1}} \\ &< \frac{1.25}{\phi^{k/2}} + \frac{3.62}{\phi^{2n+1}} + \frac{1.81\phi^m}{\phi^{2n+1}} \\ &< \frac{4.87}{\phi^{k/2}} + \frac{1.81}{\phi^{n/2}} \\ &< \frac{6.68}{\phi^{k/2}}, \end{aligned} \tag{11}$$

where

$$\Gamma_2 := (\phi+2)\phi^{-2n-1}2^{m-1} - 1.$$

Observe that $\Gamma_2 \neq 0$. Indeed, we have $2^{m-1} = \frac{\phi^{2n+1}}{\phi+2}$, which is impossible because the left-hand side is an integer whereas it can be seen that the right-hand side is irrational as $n > 351$ and $m > 240$. So, we can apply Theorem 2 to Γ_2 with

$$\eta_1 = \phi + 2, \quad \eta_2 = \phi, \quad \eta_3 = 2, \quad d_1 = 1, \quad d_2 = -2n - 1, \quad \text{and} \quad d_3 = m - 1.$$

Since $\mathbb{K} := \mathbb{Q}(\eta_1, \eta_2, \eta_3) = \mathbb{Q}(\phi)$, it follows that $d_{\mathbb{K}} = 2$. Also, we have

$$h(\eta_2) = \frac{\log \phi}{2} \quad \text{and} \quad h(\eta_3) = \log 2.$$

Moreover, one has

$$h(\eta_1) \leq h(\phi) + h(2) + \log 2 \leq \frac{\log \phi}{2} + 2 \log 2 < 1.63.$$

Thus, we can take

$$A_1 := 3.26, \quad A_2 := \log \phi, \quad \text{and} \quad A_3 := 2 \log 2.$$

Here we can take $D = 2n + 1$. Using the fact that $1 + \log(2n + 1) < 1.8 \log n$, which holds for $n \geq 9$, from Theorem 2 we get

$$\log |\Gamma_2| > -3.8 \cdot 10^{12} \cdot \log n. \tag{12}$$

Next, we put (11) and (12) together to obtain

$$k < 1.58 \cdot 10^{13} \cdot \log n. \tag{13}$$

By Lemma 9, we have

$$\log n < \log(1.7 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k) < 10.9 \log k, \quad \text{for } k \geq 350. \tag{14}$$

Using Inequalities (13) and (14), we obtain

$$k < 1.73 \cdot 10^{14} \log k.$$

It follows that

$$k < 6.3 \cdot 10^{15}.$$

We deduce that

$$n < 1.29 \cdot 10^{83}.$$

In order to reduce the above bounds of n , we put

$$\Lambda_2 = -\log\left(\frac{1}{\phi+2}\right) - (2n+1)\log\phi + (m-1)\log 2 = \log(\Gamma_2 + 1).$$

Hence, $\Lambda_2 \neq 0$ because $\Gamma_2 \neq 0$. So, we get

$$0 < |\Lambda_2| < \frac{13.36}{\phi^{k/2}}.$$

Dividing through by $\log 2$, we get

$$|(2n+1)\tau - (m-1) + \mu| < \frac{20}{\phi^{k/2}}, \tag{15}$$

with

$$\tau = \frac{\log \phi}{\log 2} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu = \frac{\log\left(\frac{1}{\phi+2}\right)}{\log 2}.$$

Now, we apply Lemma 4 with $A = 20$, $B = \phi$, and $M = 2.58 \cdot 10^{83}$. Using Maple, we find that q_{165} satisfies the hypotheses of Lemma 4, and we get

$$\frac{k}{2} < 415.14.$$

Thus, for $k \leq 830$, using Lemma 9, we obtain

$$n < 2.45 \cdot 10^{29}.$$

We apply again Lemma 4 to Inequality (15) with $A = 20$, $B = \phi$, $M = 4.9 \cdot 10^{29}$ to obtain

$$\frac{k}{2} < 157.73.$$

We obtain $k \leq 315$, which is a contradiction to the fact that $k > 350$. Therefore, we deduce that Inequality (1) does not admit any solution for $k > 350$. This completes the proof of Lemma 10. \square

Proof of Theorem 1. For this, two cases will be considered according to the values of n .

Case 1: $1 \leq n \leq k$. First, observe that for $1 \leq n \leq k$, we have $Q_n^{(k)} = 2F_{2n}$ (see Lemma 10 of [17]), where F_n is the n th Fibonacci number. Hence, Inequality (1) becomes

$$|F_{2n} - 2^{m-1}| < 2^{(m-2)/2}. \tag{16}$$

By Theorems 3 and 4, we deduce that the solutions $(F_{2n}, n, m - 1)$ of Inequality (16) are $(1, 1, 0)$, $(3, 2, 2)$, and $(8, 3, 3)$. Therefore, the solutions $(Q_n^{(k)}, k, n, m)$ of Inequality (1) are

$$(2, k, 1, 1), k \geq 2, \quad (6, k, 2, 3), k \geq 2, \quad \text{and} \quad (16, k, 3, 4), k \geq 3.$$

Case 2: $n \geq k + 1$. We assume that $n \geq k + 1$. Furthermore, considering the solutions of Inequality (16) and checking for the small values for n , we may assume that $n \geq 9$. Then applying Lemma 8, we have $m > 4$. Next by Lemma 9 we get

$$n < 1.7 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k \quad \text{and} \quad m < 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k.$$

Subsequently, we will discuss different cases depending on the size of k .

Case 2.1: $2 \leq k \leq 350$. To reduce the above bound on n (see Lemma 9), we assume that $n \geq 12$ and we put

$$\Lambda_1 := m \log 2 - n \log \alpha + \log \left(\frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)} \right) = \log(\Gamma_1 + 1).$$

By Inequality (8), we obtain

$$0 < |\Gamma_1| < \frac{16.74}{\alpha^{n/2}} < 0.94, \quad \text{for } n \geq 12.$$

Applying Lemma 6 with $a := 0.94$, $x := \Gamma_1$ we have

$$0 < |\Lambda_1| < \frac{51}{\alpha^{n/2}}.$$

Dividing through by $\log \alpha$, we get

$$|m\tau - n + \mu| < \frac{106}{\alpha^{n/2}}, \tag{17}$$

where

$$\tau = \frac{\log 2}{\log \alpha} \quad \text{and} \quad \mu = \frac{\log \left(\frac{1}{(2\alpha - 2)g_k(\alpha)} \right)}{\log \alpha}.$$

Now, we apply Lemma 4 to (17), for $3 \leq k \leq 350$, by putting

$$M = M_k := \lfloor 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot k^4 \cdot \log^3 k \rfloor, \quad A = 106, \quad \text{and} \quad B = \alpha.$$

And a quick computation with Mathematica reveals that

$$\frac{n}{2} < 76.42, \quad \text{for } k \in [3, 350].$$

Note that Lemma 4 cannot be applied to (17) for $k = 2$ because $\mu = 0$. So, for $k = 2$, we rewrite Inequality (17) as follows:

$$\left| \tau - \frac{n}{m} \right| < \frac{106}{m\alpha^{n/2}}. \tag{18}$$

If $\frac{106}{m\alpha^{n/2}} \geq \frac{1}{2m^2}$, then

$$\frac{n}{2} \leq \frac{\log(212m)}{\log \alpha} \leq \frac{\log(212 \cdot 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot 2^4 \cdot \log^3 2)}{\log \alpha} < 48.15.$$

If $\frac{106}{m\alpha^{n/2}} < \frac{1}{2m^2}$, then we apply Lemma 5 to (18) using

$$\tau = \frac{\log 2}{\log \alpha}, \quad M = 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot 2^4 \cdot \log^3 2, \quad x = m, \quad \text{and} \quad y = n.$$

After a computation using Maple, we obtain that 32 is the smallest positive integer such that $q_{32} > M$ and $a(M) = 100$. So, we have

$$\frac{1}{102m^2} < \left| \tau - \frac{n}{m} \right|. \tag{19}$$

Combining Inequality (19) with Inequality (18), we get

$$\frac{n}{2} < \frac{\log(106 \cdot 102m)}{\log \alpha} \leq \frac{\log(10812 \cdot 2.37 \cdot 10^{15} \cdot 2^4 \cdot \log^3 2)}{\log \alpha} < 52.61.$$

In all cases, we see that $n/2 < 76.42$.

Finally, using a Maple program to search all the solutions of Equation (2) with $2 \leq k \leq 350$, $0 \leq n \leq 152$, $0 \leq m \leq 215$ (as $m < 1.39n + 3.78$), and $n \geq k + 1$, we obtain the remaining solutions of this equation mentioned in our main theorem.

Case 2.2: $k > 350$. By Lemma 10, we deduce that Inequality (1) does not admit any solution in this case. This complete the proof of Theorem 1. □

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